

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH LESSONS AS A MEANS OF IMPLEMENTING METACOGNITIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. This article substantiates the strategic necessity to the importance of using digital programmes in English lessons language as a means of realising the meta-subject approach. It considers the role of the meta-subject approach in the educational process. This approach assumes that the learner not only learns a system of knowledge of a particular subject, they also learn universal ways of doing things that will enable them to find their own resources. information about the surrounding reality, analyse it and apply-The measures to be taken as necessary and as requested. Describes the measures. The following are some of the requirements for the use of digital and information technology. communication technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language with from a meta-methodological perspective.

Key words: digital technologies, meta-skills, English lessons, cognitive.

The State Educational Standard (hereinafter referred to as SES) states that a school graduate should be able to work with information. The State Educational Standard (hereinafter referred to as SES) states that a school graduate must be able to work with information, obtain the necessary information, make independent selection, analysis and synthesis of the information obtained. The modern teacher faces new tasks, the solution of which requires him/her to use innovative technologies in the educational process. Previously, the pedagogical model envisaged only the subject area, but at the present stage it is no longer relevant, since the modern teacher and student should not have information and practical limitations within one subject. New requirements for learning outcomes, prescribed in the SES, imply changes in approaches to teaching.

Metacognition provides and combines the idea of subject matter and supra-subject matter, as well as reflection. In this way, the student has the opportunity to reflect on the material. The meta-subject approach is aimed at the development of students' thinking abilities [1, p. 14].

The meta-skills are understood as universal educational actions: regulatory, cognitive The meta-skills are understood as universal learning actions: regulatory, cognitive and communicative.

Formation and development of these universal learning skills is possible

through digital technologies [1, p. 4].

Universal learning actions are understood as actions, ensuring the mastery of all key competences, which in turn form the basis of all learning and determine the ability to learn. In other words, universal learning actions are a set of all modes of action that ensure readiness and ability to independently learn new skills, as well as the regulation of cognitive activity [1, p. 22].

It is important to note that the implementation of the meta-subject approach in teaching a foreign language at school allows us to successfully work on the formation and development of intercultural communication.

With the advent of digital technologies, education has acquired a new quality, primarily associated with the ability to quickly obtain information from any point of the globe. The global digital network Internet provides instant access to the world's information resources. Digital technologies in this paper are understood as follows electronic libraries, training and testing programmes, electronic dictionaries and thesauri, telecommunication technologies, which provide an opportunity to participate in the dialogue of cultures through audio and video conferencing. participate in the dialogue of cultures.

Separate mention should be made of educational platforms. These platforms allow teachers to combine and place educational material in the form of electronic textbooks, audio, video and graphic files, use hyperlink systems, monitor students' knowledge and skills with the help of various tests, keep records of students' academic achievements in the network [5, p. 44-47].

In recent decades, the digital has become an active participant of the educational process. It helps to practice some practical skills, to organise and conduct surveys and control of students' knowledge, to perform creative tasks.

The possibility of forming universal learning actions at foreign language lessons with the help of digital technologies is more relevant than ever. It should be noted that in the age of digital technologies learning a foreign language and its practical application becomes the most accessible. Consequently, the implementation of meta-skills in lessons should not cause difficulties for both the teacher and the learner. Let us consider the regulatory skills and possibilities of their formation and development through digital technologies.

development through digital technologies. With the help of digital technologies it is possible to design a lesson, which is aimed at independent cognitive activity, to make reflection and independent correction of knowledge, as well

as self-assessment.

Formation and development of communicative skills at foreign language lessons is defined as one of the most important and significant tasks.

Digital technologies allow to practice communicative skills, promote creative rethinking of the task. Digital technologies make it possible to organise work on improving speech activity, listening and pronunciation skills, for example, by listening to authentic texts, watching video stories, etc. The digital technologies allow the students to practice communicative skills.

videos, etc. Digital programmes provide access to rich linguo-country studies material, which contributes to the development of the skills of intercultural communication. full-fledged intercultural communication [2, p. 106].

The cognitive activity of students is also actively developed through digital technologies.

cognitive activity of students is also actively developed by means of digital technologies due to the work with information sources. Students have an opportunity to choose a source from a variety of offered sources, to analyse and synthesize the obtained information [5, p. 44-47].

The above-mentioned universal learning actions and their formation and development at foreign language lessons.

formation and development at foreign language lessons implies the use of various forms of work: frontal, paired, individual.

All the above-mentioned forms of learning activities should be designed and arranged in such a way that the digital becomes a logical and very effective addition to the learning process, and not an end in itself and a determining factor.

It is necessary to outline some didactic requirements that Some didactic requirements that can be imposed on the use of digital technologies in the educational process when implementing the metaeducational approach.

One of the main principles is to clearly define the role and place, purpose and time of using digital technologies and educational resources in the classroom.

An equally important requirement is the accessibility and ease of installation of digital technologies. Modern equipment is necessary in the foreign language classroom.

It is impossible to realise metatransformativeness at the lesson, using only one type of activity. The variety of digital programmes allows to realise language phenomena, to design different communicative situations, to automate speech skills.

The teacher should follow the logical use of digital programmes in accordance with the purpose and theme of the lesson. With the correct installation and selection of digital technologies will contribute to the achievement of individualisation and intensification of independent work of students.

In addition to the above-mentioned criteria, the teacher needs to take into account the individual characteristics of students when organising independent work.

In addition to the above-mentioned criteria, the teacher needs to take into account individual characteristics of students when organising independent actions and interaction with the digital and with other students.

Undoubtedly, working with a digital increases students' interest in learning and strengthens their ability to learn.

The digital certainly increases students' interest in learning and motivation to acquire new knowledge. Independent learning of a foreign language and its practical application is possible thanks to the use of digital technologies. The use of digital technology makes it possible to learn a foreign language independently and practically.

A number of requirements must be observed.

There are a number of requirements to fulfil. A properly planned lesson with the use of digital technologies is aimed at cognitive activity, development of communicative interest, promotes activation and expansion of opportunities for independent work on mastering and practical application of a foreign language.

In conclusion, we would like to note that training with the help of digital technologies opens new opportunities for the teacher and students. Consequently, the competence of a teacher in the field of digital technologies becomes one of the most important competences of a modern specialist in the field of education. of a modern specialist in the sphere of education. At the same time, the evolution of digital technologies technology is not so much in the growth of software, but in the methodologically correct choice of content, as well as in its competent use.

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